

Special Relativity and Free Particle Quantum Mechanics Based on c-Speed Signal?

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It is well-known that special relativistic expressions for particles with a rest mass m_0 , such as: $E = m_0 c^2 / \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$ and $p = m_0 v / \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$, contain the speed of light. In other words, c is identified with light and not with an internal signal which travels at an upper bound speed which happens to match the speed of light. We have argued in previous notes that one may obtain $E = p c^2 + m_0 c^2$ from the Newtonian ideas of $KE = \frac{1}{2} m_0 v^2$ by augmenting $m_0 c^2$ through $m_0 c^2 + KE$ and $p = m_0 v$ together with the notion of complementarity of frames moving at constant relative speed $-v$ to each other. If $\frac{1}{2} m_0 v^2$, which has energy units, augments m_0 , then m_0 must be multiplied by a constant speed squared. A constant speed which is identical in all frames appears and seems to be required by the complementarity of frames viewpoint. We suggest this implies the existence of signals within a rest mass, m_0 , which travel at the speed of light. These do not appear in the nonrelativistic Newtonian expansion.

To strengthen this assumption, we consider analyzing such a signal as seen in a rest and moving frame and show that it leads to the same special relativistic results as the KE , p approach. Traditionally, this analysis is said to apply to a photon, which it does, but in the case of a rest mass there is no photon and c should apply to a signal. The key idea we wish to argue is that the change in x', t' in a moving frame is due to analysis of this signal and this even carries over into E and p values (although the nonrelativistic expansion loses c). In other words, changes in space time are due to the signal which travels with speed c and the results also pertain to a free photon. We suggest that even though E and p are strongly m_0 dependent, the space-time behaviour, even in the nonrelativistic case is signal or photon dependent and this may justify the idea of arguing that $\Delta x = \hbar/p$ and $\Delta t = \hbar/E$ for both a particle with rest mass and a photon.

In particular we suggest that x, t in the m_0 case means one must consider two cases. In the first, x, t applies to the center-of-mass of the particle and in the second, to the c speed signals. Thus, one should seek two solutions in the case of the Lorentz invariant: $-Et + px$. In the center-of-mass case, $-Et + px \neq 0$, while in the signal case, $-Et + px = 0$, with the same E, p (for the overall particle) applying to both as there are two facets to the space-time x, t .

In the photon situation, the two cases coincide. Thus, we argue that there is a connection between the wave-like behaviour of a photon and a particle with rest mass because special relativity contains the c signal for the latter and the photon is the c signal for the former.

Given that we suggest that a particle with rest mass should be associated with x, t for the center-of-mass and x, t or $\Delta x = \hbar/p$ and $\Delta t = \hbar/E$, we suggest that the latter is linked with interactions. In other words, p in this case is seen as an interaction value (and can have two directions in 1-dimension). This we argue leads to the dynamical probability $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx) = 1$, i.e. removing the interaction to reveal the center-of-mass probability for constant speed.

Special Relativity and the Speed c

We have argued in previous notes that one may consider the Newtonian idea of a particle with rest mass, m_0 , (i.e. inertia or impedance to force) and a moving particle with $KE = \frac{1}{2}mv^2$ and $p = mv$. In the Newtonian viewpoint, these are not equivalent because a force has been applied to the latter. The idea of complementarity of moving frames ($-v$ speed relative to each other) suggests that a person in a moving frame thinks he/she is at rest and the other frame is moving. This, we have argued, means that there should be an equation linking m_0 in one frame to m , KE and p in the other. This suggests associating m_0 with KE because they are both nondirectional, but then one must multiply m_0 by a constant speed squared which is the same in all frames. This speed does not appear in Newtonian mechanics, but is required for the complementarity viewpoint, i.e.

$$(m_0 c^2 + KE) - pc \approx m_0 c^2 + \frac{1}{2}mv^2 \quad ((1))$$

The approximate equation ((1)) may be shown to be more accurately:

$$E = pc + m_0 c^2 \quad \text{with } E = \frac{m_0 c^2}{\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}} \text{ and } p = \frac{m_0 v}{\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}} \quad ((2))$$

((2)) are relativistic equations and c is said to be the speed of light. There is, however, no free photon present in a particle with rest mass. Thus, we suggest that c should be considered to be a signal in m_0 which travels at the speed of light. This idea of a signal in material which travels at c is well-known in the literature (and is used in the accelerating charge problem).

At this point, it seems that the signal c does not have any relevance for space-time. We consider, however, in the next section a well-known analysis which shows that this signal is responsible for x', t' transforming according to a Lorentz transformation. This, we argue, is an important idea because it means that space-time is strongly influenced by the presence of the signal even if p and E (as given in ((2))) are not, i.e. $v \ll c$ yields Newtonian results.

Signal c and Special Relativity

((2)) is consistent with a Lorentz transformation on (pc, E) given by:

$$\begin{aligned} |g(v) \quad v/c \quad g(v/c)| \quad ((3)) \\ |vg \quad g(v/c) \quad | \quad \text{where } g(v/c) = 1/\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2} \end{aligned}$$

In the above analysis, however, there was no mention of space time x, t . We suggested above that there exists a signal which travels at speed c in all frames. We consider this signal moving a distance L in a rest frame at speed c such that

$$L = c \Delta t = ct \quad (\text{for } t_0=0) \quad (\text{rest frames}) \quad ((4a))$$

In a moving frame(-v), the signal travels at an angle such that the opposite is L and the adjacent vt'. Then:

$$\sqrt{L^2 + v^2 t'^2} = ct' \quad (\text{here we consider an initial time of } t=0 \text{ in both cases})$$

$$L/\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2} = ct' \quad ((5))$$

Thus t' and t are not the same and it is the signal with constant speed which leads to the change in time in the two frames. Traditionally, textbooks treat the signal as a free photon and the above analysis applies to one, but it also applies to a signal moving at c in all frames in a particle with rest mass. Time is changed due to the fixed speed signal even for a particle with rest mass and this is something which does not occur in Newtonian mechanics. We note, however, that if $v \ll c$, then t' and t are approximately the same. One may see from ((4)) and ((5)) that the length traveled by the signal differs in each frame. Thus, there are different space-time x',t' values due to the existence of the signal. These obey that same transformation (Lorentz) matrix ((3)), but the key point we stress is that considerations of the signal moving at c in all frames suffice to create ((3)). In other words, it is the signal with speed c which is responsible for the x',t' features and the factor $1/\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$. Thus, when considering space-time in equations, one cannot ignore a solution linked with a c signal even for a particle with rest mass.

We note that for a particle with rest mass, x' and t' will usually be considered as applying to the center-of-mass of the moving m_0 particle. We suggest, based on the above arguments, that one must consider a second solution with x',t' associated with a signal with speed c in all frames. It does not suffice to consider only one case. We further suggest that these c signals may be linked with interactions.

Photon Versus Particle with Rest Mass

A particle with rest mass m_0 seems to physically differ from a photon. One may take ((2)) and set $m_0 = 0$ to obtain:

$$E = pc \quad ((6))$$

((6)) is equivalent to a wave-equation: $c = \text{frequency} \times \text{wavelength}$ with $\text{frequency} = \text{constant} \times E$ and $p = \text{constant} / \text{wavelength}$.

((6)) represents a photon and this is a different physical object from a particle with rest mass. The fact that a photon moves like a self-wave does not necessarily a priori suggest that a particle with rest mass must do the same. The particle with rest mass contains signals moving at

c, but its E and p are mainly m_0 dependent (especially for low v values). One might argue that a photon has special wave features and a particle with rest mass does not.

The problem with this argument, we suggest, is that the notion of wavelength and frequency are space-time concepts and it is the signal travelling with speed c which is responsible for space-time changes. The frequency and wavelength features of a photon (which is a signal traveling at c) follow from:

$$-Et+px = 0 \text{ with } x/t = c \quad ((7))$$

A particle with rest mass has: $-Et+px = \text{constant} \neq 0$ in all frames ((8))

It is possible, however, to assign

$$t = \text{constant}/E \text{ and } x = \text{constant}/p \quad ((9))$$

to obtain signal intervals which make $-Et+px=0$ as in the free photon case.

In other words, we seek two solutions. One solution, $-Et+px \neq 0$ means x,t are linked to the center-of-mass of the moving m_0 particle. This point is associated with space-time, but we have argued that the $1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ factor associated with x',t' arises from the speed c signals and so there should be x,t considerations for this signal as well. We suggest that this is the $-Et+px=0$ consideration. In the rest frame, one has $E=m_0cc$ and $p=0$ and so $\Delta x \rightarrow \text{infinite}$ so that $-Et+px=0$.

In the m_0 case, Δx and Δt do not correspond to a speed c because the photon is not moving freely in space and E and p represent the entire energy and momentum. Nevertheless, spacetime features should be associated with the c signal and so we argue that ((9)) may be in keeping with such a viewpoint. The free particle quantum mechanical features ((9)) may follow from the existence of constant c signals in particles with rest mass which govern space time fluctuations regardless of the fact that rest mass exists (which dominates E and p especially for $v \ll c$). In Newtonian mechanics, Δx and Δt are tiny and so not visible, but there are cases in nature (electrons) for which they are observable. In other words, the Δx and Δt linked with signals may also be linked with interactions.

Consequences of a Center-of-mass x,t and a Signal Δx , Δt

Given that we have suggested that there are two x,t considerations, namely a center-of-mass one and signal one, we ask: What are the physical implications? We suggest that $\Delta x = \text{constant}/p$ and the signal scheme are associated with an interaction because p is proportional to an impulse. The problem is that p is directional. If one had p_1 and p_2 , one might argue that:

$$\Delta x_1 = \text{constant}/p_1 \text{ and } \Delta x_2 = \text{constant}/p_2 \quad ((10))$$

The point seems to be that overall one has p_1+p_2 (which add as vectors). Thus, one wishes to have a Δx which appropriately describes an interaction and this requires keeping in mind the direction of p . In 1-dimension, it may move to the left or right. This leads to the quantum mechanical signal-interaction type probability:

$\exp(ipx)$ ((11)) which we have called dynamical probability in previous notes.

The reason one requires a dynamical probability (i.e. one which accounts for the sign of p) is that in an AND (product) situation, one wishes to have the overall probability (p_1+p_2 vector addition) as this gives the correct p resultant magnitude to use in $\Delta x = \text{constant}/p$.

If one wishes to find information about the probability of the center-of-mass point, which is not linked to the signal type of Δx interaction range, then one may undo the dynamical probability to see what remains, i.e

$$\exp(ipx) \exp(-ipx) = 1 \quad ((12))$$

((12)) means that the center-of-mass has equal probability to be anywhere in this 1-D case. (One may introduce a $1/\sqrt{L}$ normalization into ((12)) if motion is restricted to a length L .)

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the value c which appears in relativistic E and p expressions for particles with rest mass is due to signals in the rest mass which travel at speed c in all frames. This is an idea that is well-known in the literature as such signals appear in the problem of an accelerating charge. The point we make here is that these signals are responsible for the Lorentz transformation applying to x and t . In other words, they are linked with special relativistic changes in space-time whether one has a rest mass or not. Thus, E and p may be dominated by m_0 for a particle with rest mass (for $v \ll c$), but space-time changes are strictly due to the c signal. This implies that the Lorentz invariant: $-Et+px = \text{constant} \neq 0$ for a particle with rest mass should be thought of in terms of two solutions. The first is linked with x, t representing the center-of-mass point and $-Et+px \neq 0$. The second is associated with the c speed sign and one may have intervals $\Delta t = \text{constant}/E$ and $\Delta x = \text{constant}/p$ so that $-Et+px=0$, even though $\Delta x/\Delta t$ has nothing to do with dynamical speed. $-Et+px=0$ for a photon ($x/t=c$) means that the two solutions coincide. In other words, E and p are what they are in both cases, but the c signal is linked with x and t and with $-Et+px=0$. Thus, the c signal in a particle with rest mass may be responsible for the free particle quantum mechanical intervals \hbar/E and \hbar/p .